

PROCESSES OF MICROBIOLOGICAL CHANGES IN ROOTS AND TUBER DURING STORAGE

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Abstract. One of the actual problems of today is increasing expiration date of food products and their microbiological changes for deeper learning with purpose performing a lot of practical and theoretical work.

The potato plant is infected with various fungal, bacterial and viral diseases during the growth, development and preservation of tubers. Fungal diseases include late blight, macrosporiosis, squid; in bacterial diseases, a black coloration is possible, in viral diseases - circular rot and mosaics. When tubers are stored in warehouses, arise late blight, fusarium, phomosis and wet rot.

During storage in warehouses degree of damage by root rot manifests in the form of brown spots. The bottom of this spot is dry, and the top is covered with a white mycelial bloom of the fungus. Pycnidia emerge from the mycelium in the middle of winter. When planting infected rhizomes, the plant withers or severe seed infection is observed.

The method of cold processing (preservation) of food products is based on the following: as a result temperature decreases, the vital activity of microorganism decreases, the activity of tissue enzymes decreases, as a result of which reactions in products slow down. :(breathing and ripening of fruits) and other reactions in the vital activity of microorganisms are also slow down.

Keywords: Root, tuber, storage, mode, temperature, pressure, humidity, microbiology, change, amount, soil, light, tapinambur, potato, carrot, expiration date.

Annotatsiya. Oziq-ovqat xom ashyolarining saqlash muddatlarini oshirish va ulardagi mikrobiologik o'zgarishlarini yanada chuqurroq o'rganish maqsadida ko'pgina amaliy va nazariy ishlarni amalga oshirish hozirgi kundagi dolzarb muammolardan biri hisoblanadi.

Kartoshka o'simligi o'sish, rivojlanish va tugunaklarini saqlash jarayonida turli zamburug', bakteriya, virus kasalliklari bilan kasallanadi. Zamburug' kasalliklariga fitoftorioz, makrosporioz, kalmaraz; bakteriya kasalliklariga qorason, doirasimon chirish va virus kasalliklariga mozaikani ko'rsatish mumkin. Tugunaklarni omborxonalarda saqlash jarayonida fitoftorioz, fuzarioz, fomez va nam chirish kasalligi uchraydi.

Ildizmevalaming chirishi ko'lami omborxonalarda saqlash davrida jigarrang dog'lar tarzida namoyon bo'ladi. Bu dog'laming osti quruq bo'lib, usti zamburug'ning oq mitseliy mog'ori bilan qoplanadi. Mitseliydan qish o'rtalarida piknidiyalar paydo bo'ladi. Kasallangan ildizmevalar ekilganda, o'simlik qurib qoladi yoki urug'laming yalpi kasallanishi kuzatiladi.

Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini sovuqlik bilan ishlov berish (konservalash) usuli quyidagiga asoslangan: haroratning pasayishi natijasida mikroorganizmlarning hayot faoliyati kamayadi, to'qima fermentlarining aktivligi kamayadi, bular oqibatida esa mahsulotlarda boradigan reaksiyalar sekinlashadi: (mevalarning nafas olishi va pishib o'tib ketishi va x.k.) va mikroorganizmlarning hayot faoliyatida boradigan reaksiyalar ham sekinlashadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Tugunak, ildizmeva, saqlash, rejim, harorat, bosim, namlik, mikrobiologiya, o'zgarish, miqdor, tuproq, yorug'lik, tapinambur, kartoshka, sabzi, yaroqlilik muddati.

Аннотация. Одной из актуальных проблем сегодняшнего дня является увеличение срока годности пищевого сырья и их микробиологические изменения для более глубокого изучения с целью выполнения множества практических и теоретических работ.

Растение картофеля заражается различными грибковыми, бактериальными и вирусными заболеваниями во время роста, развития и сохранения клубней. К грибковым заболеваниям относятся фитофтороз, макроспориоз, кальмариоз; при бактериальных заболеваниях возможно проявление черной окраски, при вирусных заболеваниях - круговой гнили и мозаики. При хранении клубней на складах возникают фитофтороз, фузариоз, фомоз и мокрая гниль.

Степень поражения корневой гнилью проявляется в виде бурых пятен при хранении на складах. Дно этого пятна сухое, а верх покрыт белым мицелиальным налетом гриба. Пикниды появляются из мицелия в середине зимы. При посадке зараженных корневищ растение увядает или наблюдается сильное заражение семян.

Метод холодной обработки (консервирования) пищевых продуктов основан на следующем: в результате снижения температуры снижается жизнедеятельность микроорганизмов, снижается активность тканевых ферментов, вследствие чего замедляются реакции в продуктах (дыхание и созревание плодов) и другие реакции в жизнедеятельности микроорганизмов также замедлены.

Ключевые слова: Корень, клубень, хранение, режим, температура, давление, влажность, микробиология, изменение, количество, почва, свет, тапинамбур, картофель, морковь, срок годности.

In our republic, much attention is paid to the development of the fruit and vegetable industry. The integrated development of vegetable and potato growing, horticulture and viticulture not only meet the needs of the population of our country in these products, but also satisfy the needs of processing enterprises for raw materials and will lead to an increase in the share of exports, products and foreign exchange earnings. Among plants with tuber crops in the scale of Uzbekistan, potatoes are most common cassava and sweet potato are grown more in tropical and subtropical climates.

-Potato –*Solatum tuberosum* L.-family-Solaceae

-Batat–*Ipomaea batatus* Lam–family Asteraceae

-Maniok Mahi

As these crops belong to different families, their roots are located close to each other, contain little dry substances, and therefore are poorly stored. Potato, Jerusalem artichoke and sweet potato are mainly grown in Uzbekistan from roots.

Roots contain 65-84% dry substances. The dry substances contain starch, sugar and inulin.

Table 1

Chemical composition of tuber crops, (%)

Substances	Vegetables				
	Potato	Batat	Maniok	Taro	Jerusalem artichoke
Carbohydrate	23,7	26,1	17-32	30-35	17,9
Protein	2,0	1,8	0,9-2,3	2-3	2,3
Oil	0,18	0,7	0,1-0,7	0,2-0,5	0,20

Table 2

Chemical composition of root crops, (%)

Substances	Vegetables				
	Carrot	Beet	Onion	White radish	Turnip
Carbohydrate	10,70	14,43	10,24	1,23	7,57
Protein	1,23	1,82	1,76	1,1	1,39
Oil	0,28	0,11	0,12	0,1	0,18

The potato plant is infected with various fungal, bacterial and viral diseases during the growth, development and preservation of tubers.

Fungal diseases include late blight, macrosporiosis, squid, with bacterial diseases, a black coloration is possible with viral diseases, circular rot and mosaics. When tubers are stored in warehouses there occurs late blight, fusarium, phomosis and wet rot.

The degree of damage by root rot manifests itself in the form of brown spots during storage in warehouses.

The bottom of this spot is dry, and the top is covered with a white mycelial bloom of the fungus. Pycnidia emerge from the mycelium in the middle of winter.

When planting infected rhizomes, the plant withers or severe seed infection is observed.

At the moment, there are no methods for long-term storage of products without changing their quality. But there are certain reliable substances that slow down the processes of change.

One of the most useful ways to canning perishable foods is to cold process them. When we use this method, we observe that the products change very little from their original state. It has an advantage over other methods.

The method of cold processing (canning) of food products is based on the following: as a result of a decrease in temperature, the vital activity of microorganisms decreases, the activity of

tissue enzymes decreases, as a result of which reactions in products slow down: (autolysis of meat, respiration and ripening of fruits, etc.) and reactions in the vital activity of microorganisms also slow down.

The main factor in the cooling of food products is low temperature during freezing, in addition, the transition of water in the product to a solid (ice) state, dehydration of tissues is involved.

When food is frozen, part of the water does not freeze, and this water helps the vital activity of microorganisms, so their spoilage occurs after a certain period of time.

Microorganisms have different vital activity. For example: some microorganisms live in a low-temperature environment and some die. Yeast and fungi are resistant to cold. Bacteria are not resistant to cold, they die very quickly when we freeze the environment, but their complete death is rare. The death of bacteria occurs immediately upon freezing to a solid state of the environment in which they live. If the medium is only chilled and liquid, the bacteria begin to slowly die.

Depending on the nature of heat and cold processing, food and agricultural products can be divided into:

- cooled, the temperature between the products is from 0°C to + 4°C;
- frozen, in which the temperature is below -6°C, defrosted, i.e. completely thawed, in which the temperature is above the freezing point.

Table 3

Loss of the total mass of vegetables at a temperature of 1-4°C

Indicators		Potato		White radish		Carrot	
		<i>Control</i>	<i>Experience</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Experience</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Experience</i>
Mass before storage, kg		8,1	8	6,2	6,1	4	3,9
Mass after storage, kg		7,43	7,6	5,44	5,58	3,7	3,72
Losses	In weight	0,67	0,4	0,76	0,52	0,3	0,12
	In %	8,3	5,3	12,26	8,5	7,5	4,6
	Natural losses	7,2	4,6	8,56	5,7	6,7	3,8
	Getting disease	1,1	0,4	3,7	2,8	0,8	0,8
Agricultural control (grid storage)	Losses	18,8		24,4			
	Natural losses	6,3		9,8			
	Decay losses	12,5		14,6			

The quality of food storage in refrigerating chambers to a certain extent depends on their initial germination and the condition of the refrigerating chambers. Microbial spoilage of food during storage in the refrigerator is mainly due to mold fungi. As a result of the growth and development of fungi in products, their quality not only deteriorates, but is also destroyed by the action of released enzymes. This is mainly observed during the storage of chilled products. The

development of harmful fungi stops at -9°C , but after defrosting (thawing) of the products and an increase in temperature, their vital activity is restored.

Therefore, microbiological control should be maintained at all times during the storage of products. As a result of microbiological control, the amount of damage to products from cooling chambers is determined in time and the necessary measures are taken. In addition, it is necessary to monitor the implementation of sanitary rules and technological instructions.

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